

A STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION ON CYBER ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

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Abstract

The role of entrepreneurial activities in sustaining economic development has garnered significant attention from governments worldwide. In China, innovation and entrepreneurship have become key drivers of economic growth and have been elevated to a national strategy. However, the rate of university student entrepreneurship remains relatively low, and students face employment challenges. Entrepreneurship has thus emerged as an important means to alleviate the employment dilemma among university graduates. This study explores the factors influencing cyber entrepreneurial intentions among vocational college students in Guangdong. It examines the interrelationships among three dimensions of McClelland's achievement motivation theory—achievement need, affiliation need, and power need—with self-efficacy serving as a moderating factor. Data analysis using SPSS and SmartPLS tests the proposed hypotheses, providing empirical insights to guide higher education institutions in cultivating innovative talent.

Keywords: Need for Achievement, Need for Affiliation, Need for Power, Cyber Entrepreneurial Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship contributes to economic growth and technological advancement, garnering global attention. Start-ups, as nascent commercial ventures, hold the key to technological innovation and economic expansion (Ali & Jabeen, 2022). However, data from MyCOS reveals that in developed Western nations, university graduate entrepreneurship rates reached 20%–30% as early as 2010. In China, the 2019 national undergraduate graduate entrepreneurship rate stood at 1.6%, while that for higher vocational graduates was 3.4%. This indicates that China's current university graduate self-employment rate remains relatively low, with the success rate of such ventures being particularly minimal (Yan, 2022). Guangdong Province has long prioritised university graduate entrepreneurship. Yet between 2016 and 2019, the province's overall graduate entrepreneurship rates stood at 0.65%, 0.38%, 0.39%, and 0.38% respectively – significantly below the national average exceeding 3%. Among Guangdong's vocational college graduates, entrepreneurship rates were lower than those of undergraduate graduates (Hu, 2021). Nevertheless, amid rising global unemployment and mounting employment pressures, governments in several nations are urging universities to play a more significant role in addressing this challenge. The cohort of higher education graduates in 2022 is projected to reach 10.76 million. Concurrently, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated severe macroeconomic conditions both domestically and internationally, significantly impacting employment prospects for China's university graduates (Zhou, Li & Feng, 2022). Guangdong Province has witnessed a record-breaking surge in graduate numbers, placing unprecedented pressure on the employment market and intensifying competition (Huang,

2024). Entrepreneurship has the potential to generate additional job opportunities and stimulate economic growth (Alkhalaileh, 2021).

Despite the Chinese government's implementation of policies promoting employment through entrepreneurship, research indicates that the overall entrepreneurial rate among university students remains relatively low, with individual entrepreneurial intentions still insufficiently strong. Consequently, in-depth research into entrepreneurial intentions is essential to enhance entrepreneurial rates (Gao & Chen, 2022). Research on cyber-entrepreneurship is still in its infancy (Chang, Shu, Wang, Chen & Ho, 2020). Consequently, investigating cyber-entrepreneurial intentions among vocational college students in Guangdong is highly pertinent. Initial encouraging findings regarding the positive influence of need for achievement on individual entrepreneurial intentions have since given way to considerable scepticism concerning the role of achievement motivation during the start-up phase. This indicates that the relationship between need for achievement and entrepreneurial intention warrants further exploration (Pérez-Fernández, Cacciotti, Martín-Cruz & Delgado-García, 2022). Consequently, the literature confirms that the influence of achievement need on entrepreneurial intention is contradictory and inconsistent across different contexts (Soomro & Shah, 2022). This indicates that the relationship between need for achievement and cyber entrepreneurial intention warrants further investigation. The need for affiliation constitutes a significant entrepreneurial motivator and personal need (Ramdan, Ali & Kadir, 2023). Business entrepreneurs exhibit higher needs for achievement and power, coupled with lower affiliation needs (Yee, Johari, Emang & Thoo, 2022). Elevated affiliation motivation inhibits entrepreneurial success (Maran, Bachmann, Mohr, Ravet-Brown, Vogelauer & Furtner, 2021). Power is crucial for entrepreneurial opportunities, yet entrepreneurial literature rarely focuses on power (Baker & Welter, 2020; Ramoglou, Zyglidopoulos & Papadopoulou, 2021). Power remains under-explored (Audretsch & Fiedler, 2023).

Research Questions:

- (1) What is the relationship between the need for achievement in the cyber entrepreneurial intentions in Guangdong, China?
- (2) What is the relationship between the need for affiliation in the cyber entrepreneurial intentions in Guangdong, China?
- (3) What is the relationship between the need for power in the cyber entrepreneurial intentions in Guangdong, China?

Research Objectives:

- (1) To determine the relationship between the need for achievement in the cyber entrepreneurial intentions in GD, China.
- (2) To determine the relationship between the need for affiliation in the cyber entrepreneurial intentions in Guangdong, China.
- (3) To determine the relationship between the need for power in the cyber entrepreneurial intentions in Guangdong, China.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Entrepreneurial behaviour is of paramount importance to a nation, as it fosters wealth creation and drives economic growth. Since the 1980s, numerous researchers have sought to identify factors that encourage or hinder entrepreneurial intent (Shapiro & Sokol, 1982; Bird, 1988; Bird & Jelinek, 1989). Presently, entrepreneurship is widely recognised as a powerful driver of sustained economic growth, significantly propelling development and serving as a catalyst for economic reform (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998).

Zhang Qing and Cao Wei (2010) define cyber-entrepreneurship as: the process of discovering and seizing new market opportunities, delivering novel goods or services, and creating fresh value through the utilisation of computer networks—including the internet—and other electronic network communication devices.

Entrepreneurship refers to the conscious process whereby individuals identify certain resources or acquire specific information, technologies, and opportunities. By utilising or leveraging appropriate platforms, they transform these elements in a particular manner to create value and realise their aspirations (Carland, Hoy, Boulton & Carland, 1984). Cyber-entrepreneurship plays a constructive role in addressing entrepreneurial challenges. Consequently, expanding cyber-entrepreneurship holds significant importance for economic development, poverty alleviation, and community empowerment (Hasbola, Mamat, Abdullah & Sidek, 2020). University students constitute one of the primary groups engaged in cyber-entrepreneurship. However, given the current entrepreneurial landscape, the success rate of cyber-entrepreneurship remains limited. This is because, as an entrepreneurial activity, cyber-entrepreneurship inherently involves both opportunities and risks. University students, constrained by insufficient entrepreneurial resources and limited capabilities, often struggle to undertake high-risk ventures. The difficulties encountered during entrepreneurial pursuits, coupled with a lack of entrepreneurial resilience, consequently diminish cyber-entrepreneurial intentions (Cao, 2023). Cyber entrepreneurship centres on leveraging internet technologies to create business or economic opportunities. Emerging as a revolutionary opportunity within commerce against a backdrop of technological transformation and labour market uncertainty, it operates with lower costs and reduced start-up thresholds compared to traditional brick-and-mortar enterprises. Cyber entrepreneurship has gradually evolved into a more accessible and appealing form of business creation, particularly resonating with younger generations (Chang & Chen, 2020).

The term 'cyber-entrepreneurship' has been most frequently employed in past research. Cyber-entrepreneurship may be defined as any internet-based commercial practice wherein entrepreneurs establish businesses online, utilising information technology for commercial transactions and data exchange, particularly on internet platforms. Compared to traditional entrepreneurship, cyber-entrepreneurship generally involves lower start-up costs, fewer geographical constraints, easier market entry and exit, and greater IT intensity. Cyber-entrepreneurship, as a modern and emerging concept, has been introduced within entrepreneurial studies. This new activity emerged in the 21st century and relies heavily upon technology. Cyber-entrepreneurship may be defined as any internet-based business practice

wherein entrepreneurs conduct business online, utilising information technology for commercial transactions and data exchange, particularly via internet platforms. Compared to traditional entrepreneurship, engaging in cyber-entrepreneurship is typically less costly, unrestricted by geographical boundaries, and offers easier entry and exit (Tajvidi & Tajvidi, 2021). For graduates, self-employment represents one approach to addressing unemployment (Fauzy, Yusof & Nasurdin, 2021).

2.1 Need for Achievement and Entrepreneurial Intention

The concept of achievement need was developed in the 1950s (McClelland, Atkinson, Clark & Lowell, 1958). According to McClelland (1961), the need for achievement reflects an individual's desire for personal accomplishment and success in challenging endeavours. Those with a high need for achievement and goal-attainment motivation are more likely to become entrepreneurs, as achievement need influences one's intentions. Achievement motivation and entrepreneurial behaviour are interrelated, as the former stimulates the desire to accomplish tasks excellently and outperform others. The need for achievement reflects an individual's desire for personal accomplishment and success within challenging endeavours. Those with a high need for achievement and goal-attainment motivation are more likely to become entrepreneurs, as this need influences one's intentions (McClelland, 1967). Within the context of entrepreneurial intent, specific groups exhibit a pronounced need for achievement. High achievers are more readily drawn to entrepreneurial positions and are more likely to pursue entrepreneurial employment than other roles (Saif & Ghania, 2020). Low achievement motivation correlates with low expectations, low competence, low inspiration, a tendency towards self-blame, and a propensity for failure. Consequently, it is reasonable to anticipate that individuals possessing high achievement motivation will hold a strong conviction in their capacity to establish a new enterprise, exert control over events within the establishment process, and exhibit greater entrepreneurial self-efficacy and willingness than others. Interactions between achievement motivation and other variables sometimes yield significant figures (Al-Qadasi, Zhang, Al-Awlaqi, Alshebami & Aamer, 2023). Students with high achievement motivation develop positive attitudes towards entrepreneurial intent and behaviour when supported by their educational institutions, perceiving entrepreneurship as desirable and attainable. This constitutes one of the most significant determinants of entrepreneurship (Mhd Fauzy, 2020). Research demonstrates that individuals with a high demand for achievement are likely to harbour entrepreneurial impulses (Lubada, Kusumojanto & Indrawati, 2021). Within the context of entrepreneurial intent, certain individuals harbour a need for achievement. Those with high achievement aspirations are more likely to be drawn to entrepreneurial positions and are more inclined to pursue entrepreneurial employment than other roles (Saif & Ghania, 2020).

2.2 Need for Affiliation and Entrepreneurial Intention

The need for affiliation is defined as the concern with establishing, maintaining, or restoring positive emotional relationships with others or groups (Heyns, Veroff & Atkinson, 1958). McClelland was the first to hypothesise that high power needs and low affiliation needs constitute hallmarks of effective leadership within traditional bureaucratic organisations. Given

that traditional (large-scale) organisations are characterised by a chain of command, executing resource competition and decision-making requires high power needs. A high need for affiliation diminishes a leader's capacity to make objective decisions concerning others (McClelland, 1992). The need for affiliation is a personality trait influencing an individual's entrepreneurial intentions. This demand for connectedness provides a sense of participation and belonging. The personality traits of entrepreneurs and their impact on entrepreneurial behaviour represent a previously overlooked aspect in prior research. The need for affiliation influences managerial entrepreneurial behaviour. Findings indicate that the need for affiliation positively influences managerial entrepreneurial behaviour (Parveen, Faiz, Khan, Siddique & Safdar, 2020). Individuals with high affiliation needs attempt to avoid competitive tasks, in which they often perform poorly (Veenstra, 2020). Exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities may be inhibited by high levels of affiliation motivation, with elevated affiliation motivation suppressing entrepreneurial success (Maran, Bachmann, Mohr, Ravet-Brown, Vogelauer & Furtner, 2021). Motivational characteristics influence the selection of entrepreneurial careers. Compared to non-tourism entrepreneurs, affiliation motivation exerts a moderate influence on the development of tourism entrepreneurs (Weerasinghe & Madurapperuma, 2020). The need for affiliation fosters entrepreneurial inclinations among novices, with individuals exhibiting high affiliation needs deriving diverse forms of support from connections. This enables entrepreneurs to access the information and tools required for more effective business operations, thereby achieving commercial success (Herlina, Syahchari & Rinaldi, 2022). The personality traits of entrepreneurs and their influence on entrepreneurial behaviour represent a previously neglected aspect in prior research. The need for affiliation exerts an impact on managers' entrepreneurial behaviour. Findings indicate that the need for affiliation positively influences managers' entrepreneurial behaviour (Parveen, Faiz, Khan, Siddique & Safdar, 2020).

2.3 Need for Power and Entrepreneurial Intention

The need for power manifests in the pursuit of gaining or maintaining control, and in risk-taking behaviour. Such risk-taking engenders a sense of strength, thereby satisfying the power motive (McClelland, 1975). Entrepreneurial motivation can be understood through the lens of McClelland's theory of human needs, encompassing the need for achievement, the need for power, and the need for affiliation (Wahyuningsih, 2021). Potential entrepreneurs often exhibit a high need for power, seeking to control their own destiny through the formation of a business. For successful entrepreneurs, the power motive appears indispensable; they require awareness of their objectives alongside the routes and strategies necessary to achieve them (Maran, Bachmann, Mohr, Ravet-Brown, Vogelauer & Furtner, 2021). Entrepreneurs often exhibit a high demand for power, seeking to shape their own destiny through the formation of enterprises. For successful entrepreneurs, power motivation appears indispensable (Maran, Bachmann, Mohr, Ravet-Brown, Vogelauer & Furtner, 2021). Individuals with latent desires to exercise greater power and leadership may exhibit heightened entrepreneurial inclinations (Maheshwari, 2021). However, Herlina et al. (2022) found that the need for power exerts a direct negative influence on entrepreneurial orientation. Students of business and law appear to harbour a pronounced aspiration for acquiring and exercising power, a value that exerts a

critical influence on their educational choices (Greitemeyer & Seidl, 2024). Scholars hold divergent views on power: some contend that the need for power fosters entrepreneurial motivation, yet a high power need proves detrimental to entrepreneurial management; others maintain that different groups exhibit varying degrees of power need. Furthermore, research on power and entrepreneurship remains insufficient and warrants deeper exploration.

Consequently, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H1: The stronger the need for achievement, the stronger the cyber entrepreneurial intention.

H2: The stronger the need for affiliation, the stronger the cyber entrepreneurial intention.

H3: The stronger the need for power, the stronger the cyber entrepreneurial intention.

2.4 Research Framework

This study aims to identify the factors influencing cyber entrepreneurial intentions, such as achievement motivation, affiliation motivation, power motivation, and self-efficacy, which are crucial determinants. Consequently, the research examines the impact of achievement motivation, affiliation motivation, and power motivation on cyber entrepreneurial intentions.

Figure 2.1: Research Model

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This study employs quantitative analysis and utilises stratified sampling methodology. The research population comprises Chinese higher vocational students (first, second, and third-year undergraduates). The sample size consists of 452 higher vocational students from Guangdong Province. Roasoft Sample Calculator is one of the most widely adopted software tools. Based on the 2024-2025 Guangdong Higher Vocational College Rankings published by Jinpingguo, the top four institutions were selected as research subjects, with a combined student population

of approximately 66,000. Calculations using Roasoft Sample Calculator yielded a minimum required sample size of 382 (error margin = 5%; confidence level = 95%). To mitigate the risk of invalid responses reducing the final valid sample size below 382, a sample size of 452 was selected. A stratified sampling method was employed to recruit first-, second-, and third-year students from the top four vocational colleges in Guangdong as research subjects.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Cyber entrepreneurial intention	452	1.67	5.00	3.721	0.855	-0.271	0.115	-1.112	0.229
Need for achievement	452	1.20	5.00	3.507	0.993	-0.361	0.115	-0.942	0.229
Need for Affiliation	452	1.60	5.00	3.700	0.934	-0.353	0.115	-1.035	0.229
Need for power	452	1.60	5.00	3.633	0.825	-0.270	0.115	-0.929	0.229

As shown in the table above, the statistical analysis results for each item in the questionnaire, including the number of cases, minimum value, maximum value, mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis, were employed to verify whether the data obtained from the survey conformed to a normal distribution. Whether data conforms to a normal distribution has a critical impact on subsequent analysis. Kline (1998) posits that when the absolute value of skewness is less than 3 and the absolute value of kurtosis is less than 10, the sample essentially follows a normal distribution.

The formal sample results in the table show that the absolute values of skewness for each item are generally less than 3, and the absolute values of kurtosis are generally less than 10. Both skewness and kurtosis satisfy the conditions for normal distribution, indicating that each item can be considered normally distributed. In terms of sample characteristics, this study collected 452 valid data points, representing an adequate sample size that provides a stable foundation for subsequent analysis. The minimum and maximum values for each variable encompassed the theoretical scale's potential range (1.20 to 5.00), indicating respondents provided varying degrees of feedback across all items and demonstrating sound data variability.

Furthermore, analysis of the mean values revealed the overall tendencies within the sample population. Specifically, the mean score for online entrepreneurial intention was 3.721 (standard deviation = 0.855), indicating that respondents' overall inclination towards online entrepreneurship was moderately high, demonstrating positive entrepreneurial tendencies. Regarding the three intrinsic needs, the mean for achievement need was 3.507 (standard deviation = 0.993), for affiliation need 3.700 (standard deviation = 0.934), and for power need 3.633 (standard deviation = 0.825).

All three mean values significantly exceeded the theoretical median (3), indicating that the sample group in this study generally possesses strong intrinsic motivational drivers. Among these, the mean for the need for affiliation was the highest, while the mean for the need for achievement was relatively lower.

Finally, standard deviation (Std. Dev.) reveals the dispersion of sample responses, indicating the consistency of respondents' opinions. Data shows achievement need exhibits the highest standard deviation (0.993), reflecting considerable individual variation in intrinsic motivation towards success and goal attainment. By contrast, the standard deviation for power needs (0.825) was the smallest, reflecting relatively greater consensus among the sample group regarding the desire to influence others and exert control over situations.

The standard deviation for online entrepreneurial intention was 0.855, placing its dispersion between achievement and power needs. This suggests that while overall intention is positive, the intensity of entrepreneurial willingness varies considerably between individuals. The data collected from the questionnaire can be directly utilised for subsequent statistical analyses, such as reliability and validity assessments. The data collected from the questionnaire can be directly utilised for subsequent statistical analyses, such as reliability and validity assessments.

4.2 Reliability Analysis

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Cyber entrepreneurial intention	0.894	6
Need for achievement	0.885	5
Need for Affiliation	0.868	5
Need for power	0.862	5

From the table above, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for cyber entrepreneurial intention, need for achievement, need for affiliation, and need for power in this study were 0.894, 0.885, 0.868, and 0.862 respectively, all exceeding 0.7. This indicates that the questionnaire possesses excellent reliability.

4.3 Validity Analysis

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.935
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	5048.191
	df	210
	Sig.	0.000

In conducting information condensation research using factor analysis, the first step is to assess whether the research data is suitable for factor analysis.

As shown in the table above: the KMO value is 0.935, exceeding the threshold of 0.7 required for factor analysis, indicating that the data is suitable for factor analysis research. Furthermore, the data passed Bartlett's test for sphericity ($p < 0.05$), confirming that the research data is appropriate for factor analysis.

4.4 Regression Analysis

Table 4: Results of linear regression analysis (n=452)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.005	0.166	-	6.061	0.000***	-	-
Need for achievement	0.367	0.033	0.426	10.971	0.000***	1.166	0.858
Need for Affiliation	0.267	0.037	0.291	7.174	0.000***	1.276	0.784
Need for power	0.122	0.042	0.117	2.905	0.004**	1.262	0.793
R ²	0.420						
Adjusted R ²	0.416						
F	F (3,448)=108.303,p=0.000						
D-W	2.033						
a. Dependent Variable: cyber entrepreneurial intention							
* p<0.05 ** p<0.01 *** p<0.001							

As shown in the table above, when conducting a linear regression analysis with Need for Achievement, Need for Affiliation, and Need for Power as independent variables and cyber entrepreneurial intention as the dependent variable, the model formula is derived as follows: cyber entrepreneurial intention = 1.005 + 0.367* Need for Achievement + 0.267 × Need for Affiliation + 0.122 × Need for Power. The model's R-squared value is 0.420, indicating that Need for Achievement, Need for Affiliation, and Need for Power collectively explain 42.0% of the variation in cyber entrepreneurial intention.

The F-test for the model indicates it passes the significance threshold (F=108.303, p=0.000<0.05). This confirms that at least one of Need for Achievement, Need for Affiliation, or Need for Power influences cyber entrepreneurial intention. Furthermore, testing for multicollinearity within the model reveals all VIF values are below 5, indicating no multicollinearity issues exist. Furthermore, the D-W values were close to 2, indicating no autocorrelation in the model and no correlation between sample data, thus confirming the model's soundness. Detailed analysis revealed: The regression coefficient for Need for Achievement was 0.367 (t=10.971, p=0.000<0.01), signifying that Need for Achievement exerts a significant positive influence on cyber entrepreneurial intention. The regression coefficient for Need for Affiliation is 0.267 (t=7.174, p=0.000<0.01), indicating that Need for Affiliation exerts a significant positive influence on cyber entrepreneurial intention. The regression coefficient for Need for Power was 0.122 (t=2.905, p=0.004<0.01), indicating that Need for Power exerts a significant positive influence on cyber entrepreneurial intention. The summary analysis reveals that Need for Achievement, Need for Affiliation, and Need for Power all exert significant positive influences on cyber entrepreneurial intention.

5. CONCLUSION

This study employs McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory as its core framework to explore the influence mechanisms of three fundamental social motivations—achievement motivation, affiliation motivation, and power motivation—on the online entrepreneurial

intentions of students at higher vocational colleges in Guangdong Province. Through empirical analysis of collected data and hypothesis testing, all proposed research hypotheses were supported, confirming that achievement motivation, affiliation motivation, and power motivation exert significant positive effects on vocational students' online entrepreneurial intentions. This conclusion not only validates theoretical assumptions but also provides robust empirical support and theoretical insights into understanding the psychological drivers of entrepreneurship among this specific student cohort within the context of the digital economy.

5.1 Core Research Findings and Theoretical Implications

Firstly, the most prominent finding of this study is that the need for achievement, as a core motivator, exerts the strongest positive influence on online entrepreneurial intentions. This outcome aligns closely with the fundamental tenets of achievement motivation theory, which posits that individuals with a high need for achievement crave success, embrace challenges, and take responsibility for their accomplishments. The innovative nature of the online entrepreneurship domain, characterised by high risk and high reward alongside measurable outcomes, provides an ideal “arena” for those with high achievement motivation. Within this context, they derive a profound sense of personal accomplishment by overcoming obstacles and achieving objectives. The findings of this study successfully extend and validate the applicability of achievement motivation theory beyond traditional industrial and commercial settings into the dynamic and uncertain context of online entrepreneurship, thereby enriching the theory's relevance in the digital age.

Secondly, the positive influence of affiliation needs on online entrepreneurial intentions highlights the significance of the social attributes inherent in entrepreneurial activities. Traditional perspectives might suggest that strong affiliation needs would drive individuals towards more stable, collaborative employment rather than risky entrepreneurial pursuits. However, this study's results indicate that within the context of online entrepreneurship, affiliation needs can transform into powerful entrepreneurial motivation. This is likely because online entrepreneurship is not a solitary endeavour; it relies on extensive social networks, team collaboration, client relationship management, and the cultivation of online communities. For students with high affiliation needs, the entrepreneurial process itself constitutes an endeavour to establish, maintain, and expand social connections. They pursue a sense of team belonging through entrepreneurship, seek validation from clients, and fulfil their social needs through interactions with partners and users. This finding challenges simplistic interpretations of affiliation needs, highlighting their positive role in driving collaborative, community-oriented entrepreneurship.

Finally, the positive influence of the need for power holds significant importance. It reflects students' intrinsic desire to impact others, control resources, and establish personal authority through entrepreneurial practice. Within the digital realm, this influence manifests as building an influential brand, becoming a thought leader in a field, or leading an online team. Vocational students, at a stage of heightened self-awareness and eagerness to prove their worth, are driven by power needs to establish independent status and environmental influence through creating their own online ventures, thereby realising their leadership potential.

5.2 Practical Implications and Policy Recommendations

The findings of this study offer significant practical insights for vocational colleges' entrepreneurship education, student personal development, and relevant policy formulation.

For vocational colleges: Optimising the entrepreneurship education curriculum: Entrepreneurship education should transcend basic skills training to incorporate deeper psychological motivation and character development. Curriculum design should focus on stimulating and nurturing students' achievement motivation, for instance through challenging virtual entrepreneurship projects and case studies of successful entrepreneurs to reinforce their drive for accomplishment. Differentiated and Targeted Guidance: Recognise the diversity in students' motivational structures. For students with high affiliation needs, encourage and guide them to form entrepreneurial teams and participate in start-up club activities, finding motivation through collaboration. For students with high power needs, leadership training and project management courses can be offered to channel their drive towards constructive influence. Building an entrepreneurial support ecosystem: Institutions should actively establish blended online-offline entrepreneurial practice platforms, such as incubators and industry-academia collaboration projects. These not only provide arenas for translating motivation into action but also fulfil students' need to build social connections and exert influence through practical engagement.

For individual students: This research assists vocational students in achieving profound self-awareness, clarifying the intrinsic motivations driving their career choices. Students can thereby assess whether they genuinely possess the psychological traits of an entrepreneur, enabling them to formulate career plans better aligned with their personality and inner drives. Whether choosing entrepreneurship or employment, they can identify pathways more conducive to realising their self-worth.

For government and society: Relevant authorities should consider psychological motivations when formulating policies to encourage youth entrepreneurship, particularly digital start-ups among vocational students. For instance, promotional efforts should emphasise not only economic returns but also personal fulfilment, social value, and influence. Funding and resource allocation could prioritise projects demonstrating teamwork, community service, and technological impact.

5.3 Research Limitations and Future Prospects

Despite yielding valuable findings, this study exhibits certain limitations that point towards future research directions.

Firstly, the sample was concentrated within higher vocational colleges in Guangdong Province, necessitating further validation of the findings' generalisability across different geographical regions and educational institutions of varying tiers. Secondly, whilst this study primarily examined the direct effects of three motivational factors on entrepreneurial intention, future research could incorporate additional mediating variables (such as entrepreneurial self-efficacy and risk perception) and moderating variables (such as institutional support, family

background, and sociocultural factors). This would enable a more profound exploration of the underlying mechanisms and boundary conditions through which achievement motivation influences entrepreneurial intention.

Finally, utilising cross-sectional data, this study reveals correlations among variables but cannot rigorously infer causality. Future longitudinal tracking studies or experimental designs would more clearly elucidate the dynamic development of achievement motivation and its long-term impact on entrepreneurial behaviour.

5.4 Conclusion

In summary, this empirical study demonstrates that achievement, affiliation, and power needs collectively constitute the primary psychological drivers of online entrepreneurial intentions among vocational college students in Guangdong. This finding not only validates the explanatory power of classical motivation theory within the online entrepreneurship domain but also deepens our understanding of the psychological motivations underpinning entrepreneurial behaviour among this crucial cohort of talent. Against the backdrop of a globally burgeoning digital economy and the nation's vigorous promotion of 'mass entrepreneurship and innovation', focusing on and effectively harnessing students' intrinsic achievement motivation holds crucial theoretical significance and profound practical value for cultivating versatile technical and skilled talents equipped with innovative spirit and practical capabilities.

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